

EFFECTIVE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING SKILLS TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Anatisation: Effectively using games to teach primary school students about actions through games. This will be the reason for students' time to be occupied effectively and children's interest in physical education.

Key words. Children of preschool age, game activity, mental activity, development, pedagogical direction, lesson, pedagogical methods.

Primary school-age learning activities are the leading, but not the only, activities in which students participate. Game activity does not disappear either, it only takes specific forms and has specific tasks. The unique feature of the game activity is that the content of the educational activity is successfully mastered in it. Pedagogy has always taken into account the great potential of play activities in teaching children. In the psychological-pedagogical literature, questions are raised regarding the study of different approaches to the development of the general theory of the game, referring to the works of F. Beitendyk, E. Bern, K. Gross, D. Dewey, G.

The game is one of the types of activity that is characteristic of a person and determines the development of a person. Considering the game as a need of a growing organism, we promote it in a number of pedagogical methods, it causes the action of thinking, it stimulates knowledge of the world. Children learn the world easily, freely, "without pressure" in their games. The creation of games is based on this "key", their names are: intellectual, developing, cognitive, educational, mental, educational, didactic. These types of games are nothing but learning games. S. A. Shmakov believes that the educational nature of didactic games is based on the most important example of children's game activity - the desire to act based on an imaginary situation. The fictional conditions present in the students' games serve only as a shell for games with didactic rules.

Makes children want to show them imagination, dexterity, ingenuity in mental activity. At the heart of any didactic game lies some kind of "mystery", the uncertainty of the result. The gameplay is a relaxing adventure. His motive shifts from the process of activity to the result - winning a competition or personal advantage in a mental contest.

A child's development at school occurs by involving him in various activities: here and educational work, productive work, art classes (sculpture, drawing,

singing, music, rhythm), gymnastics, sports, games, at school work state bodies. M.N. As Skatkin points out, these actions "must not be a mechanical sum, but an ensemble of their own: they must be presented in optimal proportions and interdependence."

Research in didactics is the most common, in which the game is considered as a teaching method. Since the mid-60s, the methods of didactic games have become increasingly popular in education, they stand out in the group of special methods, because they go beyond the visual, verbal and practical, and absorb their own elements.

The term "didactic game" emphasizes the pedagogical direction, reflects the diversity of its application in the educational process. It is emphasized that this is a collective, purposeful learning activity in which each participant and the team as a whole unite in solving the main task and direct their behavior to victory.

P.I. Pidkasty highlights the following structural elements in it:

- modeling of the object of educational activity;
- joint activity of game participants;
- game rules;
- decision-making in changing conditions;
- effectiveness of the applied solutions.

Noting that the didactic game as a teaching method has great potential to activate the learning process, P.I. Pidkasti emphasizes that didactic games can play a positive role in learning "only when used as a generalizing factor of a wide arsenal, not as a substitute for traditional methods."

Since the open game creates conditions for the independent development of young students in the cognitive process, it is an effective means of activating the learning process and stimulates the development of the emotional-volitional, intellectual, motor, and motivational sphere. the student activates many functional possibilities of motor activity, ensures its efficiency and development. The mechanisms of game activity in their complex interaction mobilize all aspects of the mind and psyche, realizing the need for play, the arbitrariness and freedom of behavior, the ease and freedom of communication, the magic of creativity, and the implementation of adequate actions. creates conditions for to a given action.

Using role-playing games, creating a system of images close to and understandable to the child, encouraging them to perform actions corresponding to their behavior, creates conditions for a joyful worldview and

self-awareness, stimulates the development of physical interest. educational classes.

Features specific to game activity: plot (theme, idea), content and behavior model, role, rules defining motor actions, provide design, construction and modeling of the game goal based on the processes of imitation and improvisation . systematic knowledge of the basics of motor activity.

The system of cognitive tasks in the construction of the lesson ensures the structure of the lesson and the dynamics of the child's motor development as a result of using a system of appropriate games, taking into account the different levels of work ability of students.

Based on the above facts, we can see the evidence that the game can be widely used in the development of students' motor activity. Therefore, games can be widely used during lessons.

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